

Model-Based Development and Formal Methods in the Railway Industry

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Abstract

The transition from a code-based process to a model-based process is not easy. This is particularly true for a company that operates in a safety-critical sector, where the products shall be developed according to international standards, with certified tools and controlled processes.

In this paper, we summarise the experience of a railway signalling manufacturer that decided to adopt general purpose model-based tools, namely Simulink/Stateflow and SysML, for the development of its products. The company faced challenges primarily concerning the verification of the software and the integration of the tools within the existing process. Structured development solutions and formal/semi-formal approaches (i.e., semantics restrictions, model-based testing, and abstract interpretation) were adopted to tackle the challenges. We summarise the lessons learnt during this paradigm-shift, with particular focus on the benefits and drawbacks of automatic code generation.

Index Terms

D.2.18 Software Engineering Process, D.2.4.d Formal methods, D.2.15 Software and System Safety, D.2.17.i Programming paradigms

I. THE PATH TOWARD MODEL-BASED DEVELOPMENT SUPPORTED BY FORMAL METHODS

General Electric Transportation Systems (GETS), signalling division of Florence, is a medium-size railway signalling manufacturer. About ten years ago, given the rising interest of safety-critical industries in formal methods [1], the company decided to start experimenting with formal modelling and verification. To this end, experts were contacted from the university to support the initial experiments.

Several formal tools were evaluated, but the preference of the developers fell

on a semi-formal toolsuite, namely Simulink/Stateflow [2]. The Simulink language uses a block notation for the definition of continuous-time dynamic systems. The Stateflow notation is based on Harel's Statecharts [3] and supports the modelling and animation of event-based discrete-time applications. Simulink block diagrams can be used as a framework to compose Stateflow statecharts, as it is mostly the case for the systems developed by GETS. The main reasons that drove the choice were (1) the large amount of packages available with the toolsuite – packages that could be employed throughout the whole development process – and (2) the widespread knowledge about the tools found within the company and the corporation.

Initially, the models designed through Simulink/Stateflow were used solely for requirements elicitation. In 2007, the company was attracted by the possibility of using such models also for code generation. One year after, this technology was already part of the development process. However, changing the development paradigm from *code-based* to *model-based* required changes also in the verification activities. Model-based testing and abstract interpretation were adopted in the following projects, and strict language restrictions were introduced to constrain the semi-formal semantics of the toolsuite to a formal semantics [4].

The new model-based approach allowed to speed-up the development, and, most of all, gave the possibility to handle more complex systems. As the projects grew in size, new technologies were required to rigorously handle the system requirements and the architecture level of the development. SysML, a unified modelling language for system development, was selected as the proper technology to address this issue. After three years of experience with SysML, the company has established a formal development approach that integrates SysML and Simulink/Stateflow.

II. CHALLENGES

During the story briefly summarized, the company faced several challenges that deserve some attention.

A. Modelling Language Restriction

The code used in safety-critical systems shall conform to specific safety standards, and normally the companies use coding guidelines to avoid usage of improper constructs that might be harmful from the safety point of view. When modelling and auto-coding are adopted, the generated code shall conform to the same standard asked to the hand-crafted code. The adopted code generator, named Simulink Coder, induces a tight relation between the generated code and the modelling language constructs employed. Hence, the identification of a safe subset of the modelling language is required to enable the production of code that is compliant with the guidelines, and that can be successfully integrated with the existing one.

The approach adopted by the company was first to define an internal set of modelling guidelines for Simulink/Stateflow. The guidelines were practical recommendations on the usage of the language constructs. The idea was that the C code generated from models following the guidelines would be compliant with the coding standard of the company.

The initial guidelines were based on the analysis of the code that was generated from a model previously designed for requirement elicitation. This preliminary set had the limit of being derived from a specific model, and could lack of generality. Therefore, in the projects that followed, the set was extended with other recommendations borrowed from the automotive domain (i.e., the MAAB guidelines) [5].

In order to ease formal analysis, it was finally decided to complete the modelling style guidelines by restricting the Stateflow language to a semantically unambiguous set. To this end, the studies of Scaife et al. [6], focused on translating a subset of Stateflow into the Lustre formal language, have been used. Models currently developed by the company are therefore independent from the simulation engine, and this choice has actually open the door to formal verification [4].

B. Generated Code Correctness

Safety-critical norms, such as the CENELEC EN 50128, the European standard for railway software [7], ask for a certified or *proven-in-use* translator. In absence of such a tool, like in the case of the available code generators for Simulink/Stateflow, a strategy has to be defined to ensure that the code behaviour is fully compliant to the model behaviour, and no additional improper functions are added during the code synthesis phase. The objective is to perform the verification activities at the level of the abstract model, minimizing or automating the operations on the code.

The company has adopted a model-based testing approach called *translation validation* [8], completed by static analysis by means of *abstract interpretation* [9]. With translation validation one executes test scenarios based on functional objectives at the model level. Then, he repeats the same tests on the generated code, checking that the outputs of model and corresponding code are consistent. As a final step, in order to ensure runtime error freedom, the Polyspace tool is employed to perform abstract interpretation (see [10] for the details). This technology verifies the correctness of a program on an overapproximation of the range of the program variables.

The certification authorities have considered the overall approach suitable to bypass the tool qualification required by the safety regulations. It should be noticed that the railway norms are not as specific about tool qualification as, for example, the avionic ones [11]. Therefore, companies in the railway sector are required to agree upon possible strategies with the certification authorities.

C. Multiple Formalisms

Safety-critical systems are normally large, complex platforms with several interacting units and architectural layers. To manage such complexity, their development is based on multiple levels of abstraction, and different models with different granularities are required. Indeed, a model that is used for code generation is hardly usable to reason at system design level.

Simulink/Stateflow do not support a flexible hierarchical development approach, and system designers need to adopt other modelling languages that can express the higher abstractions inherently required by the process.

In the experience of the company, this issue has been addressed through the adoption of the SysML language [12]. After an initial experience with the TOPCASED tool for SysML [13] – which at that time was not considered mature for industrial usage – the company adopted the Magic Draw platform [14]. It is worth mentioning that the early projects that were employing code generation did not use any SysML support. The need for such a language came when the systems produced by the company started to radically increase in terms of complexity (to have an idea, when the number of lines of code exceeded 100 000).

The current role of SysML is as follows. Right after requirement elicitation, requirements appear like unstructured *post-it* notes in the blackboard of the requirements manager. High-level system requirements are identified among this initial set, and are expressed in the form of SysML *requirement diagrams*. These diagrams allow specifying hierarchical relationships and dependencies among single requirements, and the chaotic post-it view is replaced by a structured graph-like model.

Then, *block diagrams* are employed to specify the interfaces of the system modules that are supposed to implement the requirements. An approach based on decomposition is adopted, which allows specializing each module into sub-modules towards the actual implementation. Each module has some high-level requirements apportioned to it. If needed, requirements are also refined into lower-level requirements when modules are specialized.

The SysML models are structured into *packages* residing in a single root model. Each package corresponds to a phase of the V-based development process prescribed by the CENELEC norm for railway safety-critical systems [7]. Therefore, there is a well defined mapping between process phases and the diagrams that have been used in each phase.

SysML could be in principle employed also to define the behaviour of the actual implementation and to generate code. However, modelling and

simulation at behavioural level is much faster and more flexible with Simulink/Stateflow, and the generated code has higher quality. Therefore, the role of SysML ends at the software architecture level.

D. Process Integration

Product development is performed by companies by means of processes, which define a framework made of tasks, artifacts and people. Introduction of new technologies in an established process requires adjustments to the process structure, which shall maintain its coherence even if changes are applied. This is particularly true in the case of safety-critical companies, whose products have to be validated according to normative prescriptions. Hence, a sound process shall be defined in order to integrate modelling and code generation within the existing framework.

Fig. 1. Overview of the model-based development process adopted

An enhanced V-based process has been defined, as depicted in Fig. 1. The process embeds two verification branches: one for the activities performed on the models, and the other for the tasks concerning source code and system. In the figure, we highlight the parts that strictly concern software development – based on Simulink/Stateflow modelling – and the parts that are related to system development – based on SysML modelling. The two process fragments overlap in the SW Requirements phase and in the SW Model Architecture phase. Indeed, software requirements are expressed in SysML, as well as the software architecture. An equivalent architecture is expressed through Simulink in the form of interacting blocks, which are the functional modules (i.e., the components) of the model. SysML requirements are manually traced to the Simulink model. In the Model Module Design phase, the Simulink blocks are refined into Stateflow statecharts.

It is worth noting that the process is somehow adaptable to both manual coding and to auto-coding. After the SysML modelling activities, one can decide to adopt either hand-crafted code or Simulink/Stateflow modelling to develop the application. Indeed, in some applications (e.g., firmware, systems with limited software, platform with strong dependencies from legacy code), the code generation technology is considered not convenient, and hand-crafted code is normally employed.

III. LESSONS LEARNT

Facing the challenges of model-based development made the company learn some important lessons.

A. Abstraction

Models allow working at a higher level of abstraction, and they can be manipulated better than code. The company experienced the actual relevance of this statement in the transition from code-based to model-based testing. The model-based testing approach adopted has allowed defining behavioural test scenarios at component level without disrupting the model structure. This approach would have been impracticable on hand-crafted code. Indeed, with hand-crafted code, it is common to perform tests on single functions, while it is more complex to identify the functions that participate to the behaviour of

a software component. With models, one builds the system already in terms of components. Therefore, identification and testing of components comes in a natural way.

The company learnt also that abstraction is a delicate concept that has to be carefully handled. The proper degree of abstraction has to be identified in order for an artifact to be useful. For example, in the initial experience with SysML, requirement diagrams with natural language requirements were adopted throughout the process until the lowest level of model detail. At this point, their content was basically equivalent to the Simulink/Stateflow models. The level of abstraction of such requirements had to be raised, since they appeared to be redundant and any slight modification to the models would have implied a modification to the requirements.

B. Expressiveness

Graphical models are closer to the natural language requirements. At the same time, they are an unambiguous mean to exchange or pass artifacts among developers. This observation has been enlightened by the main model-based development experience of the company reported in [4], where the project passed from the hands of its first main developer to another developer within one month only and with very limited support.

The previous experience of the company was that, if someone was the father of a piece of software, he would have remained the one and only repository of the knowledge for that software. This is a common problem in many small and average size companies. It negatively affects both the company itself, which has to rely on a single person to actually modify and reuse the software, and the developer, who normally wish to extend his competencies to go beyond his initial fragment of code.

C. Cohesion & Decoupling

The automatically generated software is composed by modules with higher internal cohesion and better decoupling with respect to manual coding. Interfaces among functionalities are based solely on data, and the control-

flow is simplified since there is no cross-call among different modules. Decoupling and well-defined interfaces have helped in easing the outsourcing of the modelling activity, which is a relevant aspect in the development of products that have to tackle time-to-market issues.

D. Uniformity

The generated code has a repetitive structure, which facilitates the automation of the verification activities. When strict modelling guidelines are defined, one could look at the generated code as if it would be the software always written by the same programmer. Therefore, any code analysis task can be tailored on the artificial programmer's design habits. As a witness for this observation, consider that the abstract interpretation procedure adopted to reveal runtime errors resulted actually profitable on the generated code only, since systematic analysis on hand-crafted code was made harder by its variable structure and programming style.

Uniformity is guaranteed also at the process level with the support of SysML. Employing a unified modelling language – and a single tool – in great part of the development phases eases all those activities that involve the interfaces among the phases. Indeed, in a V-based process, the output artifact of a phase is the input artifact for the following one. The use of SysML has somehow made rigorous this handing over.

E. Traceability

Software modules are directly traceable with the corresponding blocks of the specification modelled with Simulink/Stateflow. Traceability is a relevant issue in the development of safety-critical systems, since any error has to be traced back to the process task, or artifact defect, that produced it. The structured development approach introduced, with the support of the Simulink/Stateflow toolsuite, has allowed defining navigable links between the single code statements and the requirements.

At the SysML level, traceability involves the links between requirements diagrams and related SysML diagrams. Traceability links are manually defined through simple drag and drop operations, and traceability matrixes are automatically generated. In a traditional process, traceability matrixes are

manually edited, with no tool support and consequent maintainability issues.

In the experience of the company, when change requests are issued by a customer, they normally involve system-level requirements. The tool support available with a model-based approach allows tracing the changes from such requirements to the module-level requirements and the corresponding models. Therefore, both the developers and the requirements managers have a complete view of the impact of the change requests. Instead, in a traditional process, one would have to inspect the traceability matrix and check the artifacts that are affected by the change request, an activity that can be rather time consuming and error prone (unless supported by proper automated tools).

Automatic traceability support among SysML and Simulink/Stateflow models is still an open issue, since there is currently no tool that implements such a feature.

F. Documentation

For safety-critical systems, the official documentation associated to each process phase and artifact is as important as the actual system. The certification of these product is mainly based on the inspection of such a documentation by an external authority. It is therefore important to have a documentation that is formal, expressive and up-to-date with the product status.

In the process currently implemented by the company, both SysML and Simulink/Stateflow models are used to provide documentation for the process artifacts.

Simulink/Stateflow models with proper comments are used to automatically generate the software documentation. Hence, documentation and software are totally aligned.

On the other hand, SysML diagrams are integrated into the manually edited documentation. Documents can be automatically generated from SysML as

HTML pages, but certification authorities normally require to have paper-like documents focused on text, rather than navigable HTML documents with SysML models. The main reason is that the certification authority normally enters at the end of the development process to validate compliance with the standards, and wants to analyse the process as a sequential history - a paper-like document - and not as an interwoven graph of HTML pages.

The integration of the SysML models into the documents poses maintainability issues. Indeed, if the model changes, the change is not automatically reflected by the documentation. However, the one-to-one correspondence between SysML packages and process phases – and associated documents – eases the manual update of the documentation. Furthermore, the traceability links between models in different packages helps the maintenance of the cross dependencies among documents. When a model is changed, the model package clearly identifies the document that has to be modified. Then, one can follow the traceability links to retrieve the other models that are affected by the change. Such models belong to packages with associated documents. Hence, the link among models indirectly create a relationships among documents, and the overall SysML model becomes a sort of navigable index for the process documentation.

G. Verification Cost

The introduction of the new development process has allowed the reduction of the cost of the verification activities, while ensuring greater confidence on the product safety. When passing from traditional code unit testing based on *structural* coverage objectives, to testing based on *functional* objectives aided with abstract interpretation, it was possible to reduce the verification cost of about 70%. The new approach was comparable to the previous one in terms compliance to the CENELEC EN 50128 requirements on verification, but resulted much more cost-effective [10].

Though consistent cost improvements have been achieved, manual test definition is still the bottleneck of the process, requiring about 60-70% of the whole unit-level verification cost. Preliminary experiments with formal

verification applied at unit-level have shown that this technology might considerably reduce the verification cost for the majority of the requirements. Indeed, the recent experiments with formal verification by means of Simulink Design Verifier have shown that the verification cost can be further reduced by 50-66% [4].

H. Control

The structured development has allowed achieving greater control over the components and, finally, to produce software with less bugs as the input to the verification activities. This is witnessed by the number of bugs found by verification, which decreased from 10 to 3 bugs per module when the company introduced a rigorous model-based process.

I. Complexity

The main drawback encountered in introducing code generation has been the *size* and overall *complexity* of the resulting software. Though these aspects were not complicating the verification activities, they posed challenges from the performance point of view.

Real-time constraints for railway signalling systems are not so demanding as are for other kinds of embedded systems, and the typically required response times are in the range of hundreds of milliseconds. However they are reactive systems that, might a failure occur, shall activate failure recovery procedures in a limited amount of time in order to reach the safe state. The reaction time is influenced by the main execution time. In the first experiments with code generation this execution time resulted four times higher compared to the time required by the execution of the corresponding hand-crafted code. In order not to abandon the advantages of auto-coding, in the discussed case an hardware upgrade actually solved the problem.

However, during the design of new, more complex systems, this issue has to be taken into account while defining the hardware architecture. The hardware designer shall consider that the code is larger in size, and there is less flexibility in terms of optimizations at source level (we recall that optimizations at compiler level are not recommended for the development of safety-critical systems): when designing the platform, a larger amount of

memory has to be planned if one wants to employ automatic code generation.

J. Knowledge Transfer

Some lessons have been learned also from the *knowledge transfer* point of view. The research activity has been performed according to the following research management model.

On one side there is a research assistant who comes from the university and is fully focused on the technology to be introduced. On the other side there is an internal development team, which puts the research into practice on real projects when the exploratory studies are successful.

The results obtained during this experience would have not been possible through intermittent collaborations only. Moreover, they would have been hardly achieved if just an internal person would have been in charge of the research. In order to separate the research from the time-to-market issues, the independence of the research assistant from the development team has to be preserved. Large companies can profit from dedicated internal research teams, or even entire research divisions. Instead, medium-size companies often have to employ the same personnel for performing research explorations, which are always needed to stay on the market, and for taking care of the day-by-day software development. We argue that the research management model adopted in the presented experience, based on an academic researcher independently operating within a company, can be adapted to other medium-size companies with comparable results.

IV. CONCLUSION

General Electric Transportation Systems was able to understand the benefits of a model-based process aided with formal methods especially thanks to the initial enthusiasm associated to code generation. Such technology showed its potentials in few months, and its adoption was straightforward. Then, a butterfly-effect in the process occurred that brought to the adoption of other techniques, such as model-based testing, abstract interpretation and system modelling with SysML.

Formal verification is not part of the GETS development process yet. We can observe that nevertheless formal verification with model checking is often the subject of the first experiments of companies with something formal, especially in the safety-critical systems domain. In many cases, they did not go much further than these initial experiments, notwithstanding the achieved evidence of lower verification costs. Indeed, the adoption of formal verification without intermediate steps is not common: the difficulties related to the steep learning curve required by formal methods often tend to discourage industrial practitioners and managers, who need to see the evidence of productivity gains within short time.

The reported experience shows that may be more effective to start with less formal tasks (i.e., *code generation*), and later adopt more formal tasks, such as *verification*, when the company has matured a full awareness of the actual benefits of “being formal”.

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